

Leading collaborative research on video corpora. CANEVAS tools and methods.

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The analysis of audiovisual corpora is a fundamental issue for Humanities and Social Sciences. For example, it is a long-standing issue in History, where film analysis is widespread and even institutionalized for decades (Ferro 1974; Delage / Guigueno 2004). These practices also concern a large diversity of research fields such as Sociology (Sebag / Durand 2020), or Education Sciences (Leblanc / Ria / Veyrune 2013), added to other fields such as Media Studies or Film Studies (Fleckinger 2018), to which the use of audiovisual content is native. However, the shift to digital technologies has significantly modified modalities and potentialities of the audiovisual analysis. With the growing production of digital videos and movies (Côté-Lapointe 2019), but also their increased broadcasting on the Internet, new horizons are emerging for research (Burgess / Green 2018).

For digital humanists, the development of technological devices adapted to their research practices is mandatory. For example, the *Mediascope* software of the French *Institut National de l'Audiovisuel* has provided a solution adapted to enter the analysis of their collections. Other solutions, essentially developed for experimental purposes within the framework of research projects, have also coexisted (Bourgatte / Tessier 2017). However, despite the length of time, researchers working on audiovisual corpora often still lack tools and methods adapted to their practices. More broadly, they also lack norms and standards that allow them to make their work accessible in a long-term manner. This explains why some forms of "DIY" remain.

How should we treat, investigate and analyze the contemporary profusion of digital audiovisual documents? This is the purpose of the "Huma-Num CANEVAS consortium" inaugurated in 2022, which brings together researchers from different disciplines whose common interest is precisely to handle video corpora in their research. Implementing research in social sciences and humanities based on audiovisual corpora implies addressing different types of key issues: finding the best suited search and analysis tools, hosting and archiving audiovisual data, and sharing valorization strategies. All these topics are at the heart of numerous experiments but have not yet found long-term answers.

The CANEVAS consortium first took shape around the question of annotation. As note-taking is the natural support of any research activity, it is indeed essential for the researcher to have, during his/her activities, the possibility of associating analyses or comments with the materials that constitute his/her corpus. This is made possible, among others, by tools such as *Celluloid* or *E-Spectator* :

Figure 1: Screenshot Celluloid (<https://celluloid.huma-num.fr/>)

Figure 2: Screenshot E-Spectateur (<https://espectateur.huma-num.fr/>)

The question of long-term archiving of large data sets was then raised, searching for solutions offering similar options to those offered by platforms such as Youtube or Vimeo, but in an open source / decentralized way, which is made possible, for example, by *PeerTube* instances.

Figure 3: Screenshot PeerTube (<https://celluloid-media.huma-num.fr/>)

Finally, there is the question of interoperability of the annotations (for example, with common metadata formats such as IIIF, which is currently applied to images and which is also being experimented with 3D, but not yet with video corpora).

In line with the FAIR principles, Canevas is committed to developing generic, free and open-source tools and common standards that should open new perspectives by simplifying procedures in an open science dynamic.

A selection of tools and methods identified by the Canevas research community is curated in the consortium white paper (Besson / Lavorel 2023). In this paper, researchers from different fields have selected functional applications suitable for research and pedagogy in the humanities. The results of this collaborative research show that 4 of these tools are only usable locally and thus

appropriate for individual work. Two tools allow online collaborative work by relying on proprietary services (Youtube/Vimeo), which are therefore not DH compliant. Only one tool (Celluloid), allows remote collaborative work with a free and open-source platform (Peertube). Moreover, these tools all allow the export of annotations in various formats (JSON, CSV, RSS, XML), which is essential in a logic of sharing research results, but no common standard has been adopted yet.

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	Adren	ArchiVidéo	Celluloid	Celluloid	Celluloid	Celluloid	Celluloid
Description
Infos (description / genre)
Système	Linux, Mac OS X	Linux, Mac OS X	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Code source	Propriétaire	Propriétaire	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Installation	Sur le poste de travail	Sur le poste de travail	Application web				
Mise à jour des vidéos	Local						
Annotation audio-vidéo, image fixe, graphique	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Annotation collaborative	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Annotation pédagogique	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Contexte d'utilisation	Recherche, enseignement	Recherche	Recherche, enseignement				
Documentation (manuel, tutoriel)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Niveau d'expertise	Intermédiaire à avancé	Intermédiaire à avancé	Intermédiaire	Intermédiaire à avancé	Intermédiaire	Intermédiaire	Intermédiaire
Exportation des annotations / format	CSV, JSON, XML, RSS	CSV, JSON, XML, RSS	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A

75. TABLEAU RÉCAPITULATIF L'ANNOTATION VIDÉO POUR LA RECHERCHE - 77

Table 1: This table summarizes the comparison of 7 tools useful for analyzing and annotating audiovisual corpora. The detailed analysis of these softwares is available in the white paper, freely accessible on the Hal open archive, via this QR code:

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